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FACTORS AFFECTING CUSTOMER SATISFACTION IN AFTER SALES SERVICE IN AUTOMOBILE INDUSTRY (PASSENGER CAR SEGMENT)

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ABSTRACT

The automobile industry accounts for 22 per cent of the country's manufacturing gross domestic product (GDP). The Indian auto industry is one of the largest in the world with an annual production of 21.48 million vehicles in FY 2013-14.

The entry of global auto-majors into India has significantly altered the automobile-manufacturing scenario in the country. The changes in design and adaptation of international technologies have enabled the Indian automotive industry to compete globally, and thus are also exposed to global challenges. Alongside the challenges, the trend also presents a plethora of opportunities to Indian automotive industry, which needs to be capitalized, so as to emerge as a successful global player.

Five independent variables have been considered to judge customer satisfaction in after sales service in automobile industry, which are Service Cost, Quality of Repair, Speed/Promptness in the Service, Location of the Service Centre and Behaviour of the Management. The results indicate that there is strong association between customer satisfaction and the independent variables. Those variables are important for business organizations to make their customers happy and pleased so far as after sales service is concerned. The satisfied customers will remain loyal and always have a positive notion towards the company and its service.

Key words: *Customer Satisfaction, After Sales Service, Automobile Industry*

INTRODUCTION :

The automotive industry is increasingly becoming the cynosure of the manufacturing sector across the globe. The attention and importance to the automotive industry in the economic development and planning policies of Government and its agencies has also witnessed significant uprise. The industry has been evolving over the years, meeting up with challenges as diverse as transitions, consolidations and restructuring, and thereby adapting to the new market conditions. In the last few years, the world automotive industry has changed its locational preferences due to various reasons. Earlier, the automotive industry was largely confined to the triad - North America, Europe and Japan; however, with the emergence of some vibrant developing economies, like Brazil, India and China, the global automotive industry has been considering a different growth perspective, and has been relocating the operations.

These growing developing economies has been evolving as the manufacturing hub, as also the newfound markets, for the global majors like Ford, General Motors, Chrysler, Toyota, Honda, Nissan and BMW, who are competing to enhance their market share in these markets. Increasing growth in GDP and the growing disposable income has catapulted these emerging economies as market for automotives, while the low cost of operations and skills in design and R&D made them as destinations for investment and manufacturing operations.

An expanding middle class, a young population, and an increasing interest of the companies in exploring the rural markets have made the two wheelers segment (with 80 per cent market share) the leader of the Indian automobile market. The overall passenger vehicle segment has 14 per cent market share. India is also a

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substantial auto exporter, with solid export growth expectations for the near future. Various initiatives by the Government of India and the major automobile players in the Indian market is expected to make India a leader in the Two Wheeler and Four Wheeler market in the world by 2020.

Market Size

Sales of commercial vehicles in India grew 5.3 per cent to 52,481 units in January 2015 from a year ago, according to Society of Indian Automobile Manufacturers (SIAM). Sales of cars also grew for a third month in a row to 169,300 units in January 2015, up 3.14 per cent from the year-ago period. Car market leader Maruti Suzuki India witnessed 8.6 per cent higher sales at approximately 118,551 units in February 2015, out of which 107,892 were sold in domestic market and 10,659 units were exported. Hyundai Motor India Ltd (HMIL) reported a 2.4 per cent growth in total sales at 47,612 units in February, compared with 46,505 units in the same month last year. In the two-wheeler segment, Hero MotoCorp witnessed sales of 484,769 units in February 2015. TVS Motor Co posted 15 per cent higher sales at 204,565 units against 177,662 units.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The online search behaviour of consumers mirrors the offline world. In a recent survey on online consumers, query volumes on Google search see a 38% increase over first half of the year as Indian consumers tend to make auto purchases during the festive season (2009 to 2010). Indians are also more research oriented when it comes to auto related purchases, with 65% Indians using the Internet as the first place to do their research before deciding on the vehicle of their choice. This is ahead of consumers in mature markets like US and Europe where only 62% of users use Internet as their first stop. In cars, entry and mid segment cars in the price range of (2 lakhs upto 6 lakhs), the highest selling car category by volumes in India, was also the most-searched category registering over 50% year on year growth in query volumes. Customer satisfaction is an ambiguous and abstract concept and the actual manifestation of the state of satisfaction will vary from person to person and product/service to product/service. Customer satisfaction, a term frequently used in marketing,(American Marketing Association) is a measure of how products and services supplied by a company meet or surpass customer expectation. Customer satisfaction is defined as "the number of customers, or percentage of total customers, whose reported experience with a firm, its products, or its services (ratings) exceeds specified satisfaction goals." Farris(2010).

The state of satisfaction depends on a number of both psychological and physical variables which correlate with satisfaction behaviors such as return and recommend rate. The level of satisfaction can also vary depending on other options the customer may have and other products against which the customer can compare the organization's products. A business ideally is continually seeking feedback to improve customer satisfaction. "Customer satisfaction provides a leading indicator of consumer purchase intentions and loyalty."Farris(2010). "Customer satisfaction data are among the most frequently collected indicators of market perceptions. Their principal use is twofold:" "Within organizations, the collection, analysis and dissemination of these data send a message about the importance of tending to customers and ensuring that they have a positive experience with the company's goods and services." Secondly, "Although sales or market share can indicate how well a firm is performing currently, satisfaction is perhaps the best indicator of how likely it is that the firm's customers will make further purchases in the future.

Work done by Parasuraman et.al., between 1985 and 1988 provides the basis for the measurement of customer satisfaction with a service by using the gap between the customer's expectation of performance and their perceived experience of performance. This provides the measurer with a satisfaction "gap" which is objective and quantitative in nature. Work done by Cronin and Taylor propose the "confirmation/disconfirmation" theory of combining the "gap" described by Parasuraman, Zeithaml and Berry as two different measures (perception and expectation of performance) into a single measurement of performance according to expectation.

However, according to Murthy D. N. P., et al. (2004) customer dissatisfaction can arise due to poor performance of the purchased item and/or the quality of warranty service provided by the manufacturer. In either case, it

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The number of factors extracted can also be determined in a way so that the cumulative percentage of variance extracted by the variables reaches a satisfactory level. *Table – 2* below shows the total variance explained.

TABLE – 2: Total Variance Explained									
Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.558	51.155	51.155	2.558	51.155	51.155	2.166	43.328	43.328
2	1.079	21.571	72.727	1.079	21.571	72.727	1.470	29.399	72.727
3	.581	11.612	84.338						
4	.488	9.766	94.105						
5	.295	5.895	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

In the above table, the cumulative percentage of variance extracted by three factors is 72.727% which is quite satisfactory. Then the rotated component matrix is conducted with the above variables. The results are displayed below in *Table – 3*:

TABLE - 3

Rotated Component Matrix^a		
	Component	
	1	2
SPEED / PROMPTNESS IN THE SERVICE	.841	
QUALITY OF REPAIR / SERVICE	.826	
BEHAVIOUR OF THE MANAGEMENT	.759	
LOCATION OF THE SERVICE CENTRE		.923
COST INVOLVED IN THE SERVICE		.727

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

a. Rotation converged in 3 iterations.

However, from the results obtained in the *Rotated Component Matrix in Table – 3* above, all the five variables can be accepted for further analysis. These variables were then subjected to reshuffle and reduction. This reshuffle and reduction is possible because the variables are related. The rating given to any one variable is partially the result of the influence of other variables.

In the rotated component matrix table, broadly two factors have been identified consisting of five variables. These are:

Factor - 1 consisting of variables like “*Speed/Promptness in the Service, Quality of Repair and Behaviour of the Management*” is loaded as 0.841, 0.826 and 0.759 respectively.

Similarly, Factor - 2 consisting of variables like “*Location of the Service Centre and cost involved in the service*” is loaded as 0.923 and 0.727 respectively.

In the rotated component matrix Factor 1 has high coefficients for variables “**Speed/Promptness in the Service, Quality of Repair and Behaviour of the Management**” and Factor 2 has high coefficients for variables “**Location of the Service Centre and Cost involved in the Service**” and therefore the said variables are aggregated in their respective factors.

The naming of the Factors are then carried out which is elaborated in *Table – 4*.

TABLE - 4
NAMING OF THE FACTORS

FACTOR 1

SPEED/PROMPTNESS IN THE SERVICE	SERVICE RESPONSIVENESS
QUALITY OF REPAIR	
BEHAVIOUR OF THE MANAGEMENT	

FACTOR 2

LOCATION OF THE SERVICE CENTRE	ECONOMIC AND CONVENIENT SERVICE DELIVERY
COST INVOLVED IN THE SERVICE	

In the above table, Factor 1 is labeled as “*Service Responsiveness*”, Factor 2 is labeled as “*Economic and Convenient Service Delivery*”.

Finally after factor analysis, the results are required to be validated. For the same, an important statistical tool like regression analysis has been used showing R – square values.

Regression Analysis

Regression analysis is performed with dependent variable as “*Service Responsiveness*”

(*Factor 1*) and independent variables as **Speed/Promptness in the Service, Quality of Repair and Behaviour of the Management** to see the fitness of the model.

Table – 5A shows R-Square value of 0.961 which is reasonably fit for the analysis. From the *ANOVA Table (Table No. 5B)*, it appears that the three predictor variables are not all equal to each other and could be used to predict the dependent variable, Service Responsiveness (*Factor 1*) as is indicated by F value of 915.331 and strong significance level of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$). Further from the next table (*Table No. 5C*), the results show that all of the variables are significant ($p < 0.001$) with high Beta (0.438, 0.439 and 0.303) and t value (18.209, 18.922 and 13.034).

Regression factor 1

TABLE 5A

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.980 ^a	.961	.960	.19975508

a. Predictors: (Constant), SPEED / PROMPTNESS IN THE SERVICE, QUALITY OF REPAIR / SERVICE, BEHAVIOUR OF THE MANAGEMENT

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**TABLE 5B
ANOVA^b**

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	109.571	3	36.524	915.331	.000 ^a
	Residual	4.429	111	.040		
	Total	114.000	114			

a. Predictors: (Constant), SPEED / PROMPTNESS IN THE SERVICE, QUALITY OF REPAIR / SERVICE, BEHAVIOUR OF THE MANAGEMENT

b. Dependent Variable: REGR factor score 1 for analysis 1

**TABLE 5C
Coefficients^a**

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-10.294	.206		-50.018	.000
	QUALITY OF REPAIR / SERVICE	.985	.052	.439	18.922	.000
	BEHAVIOUR OF THE MANAGEMENT	.732	.056	.303	13.034	.000
	SPEED / PROMPTNESS IN THE SERVICE	.831	.046	.438	18.209	.000

a. Dependent Variable: REGR factor score 1 for analysis 1

Another Regression Analysis is performed with dependent variable as **“Economic and Convenient Service Delivery” (Factor 2)** and independent variables as **Location of the Service Centre and Cost involved in the Service** to see the fitness of the model.

Table – 6A shows R-Square value of 0.958 which is also reasonably fit for the analysis. From the **ANOVA (Table No.6B)**, it appears that the two predictor variables are not all equal to each other and could be used to predict the dependent variable, Economic and Convenient Service Delivery (**Factor 2**) as is indicated by F value of 1.269E3 and strong significance level of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$). Further from the next table (**Table No. 6C**), the results show that all of the variables are significant ($p < 0.001$) with high Beta (0.746 and 0.371) and t value (33.714 and 16.76).

Regression factor 2

**TABLE 6A
Model Summary**

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.979 ^a	.958	.957	.20743197

a. Predictors: (Constant), LOCATION OF THE SERVICE CENTRE, COST INVOLVED IN THE SERVICE

TABLE 6B
ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	109.181	2	54.590	1.269E3	.000 ^a
	Residual	4.819	112	.043		
	Total	114.000	114			

a. Predictors: (Constant), LOCATION OF THE SERVICE CENTRE, COST INVOLVED IN THE SERVICE

b. Dependent Variable: REGR factor score 2 for analysis 1

TABLE 6C
Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-5.221	.106		-49.248	.000
	COST INVOLVED IN THE SERVICE	.398	.024	.371	16.760	.000
	LOCATION OF THE SERVICE CENTRE	.986	.029	.746	33.714	.000

a. Dependent Variable: REGR factor score 2 for analysis 1

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

From the statistical result, it is found that Factor-1 named “*Service Responsiveness*” consisting of variables like **Speed/Promptness in the Service, Quality of Repair and Behaviour of the Management** and Factor-2 named “*Economic and Convenient Service Delivery*” consisting of variables like **Location of the Service Centre and Cost involved in the Service** are significantly related to the customer satisfaction. These two factors are important in delivering an acceptable service performance that will be able to make the customer satisfied and delighted. According to the model of customers’ satisfaction by Zeithaml and Bitner (2008), quality service is the focus of assessments reflecting the customers’ perception on satisfaction which is in line with the findings of this study where *Service Responsiveness*” and “*Economic and Convenient Service Delivery*” are the two identifiable areas for providing quality service which in turn will satisfy the customers in the automobile sector.

However, “Satisfaction is a phenomenon expressing that the performance and benefits of the products exceed the expectations of the customers. Customer satisfaction increases the existing customer loyalty, awareness of the people about the firm, decrease the price flexibility, the cost of gaining new customers and prevent the customer being affected from competitive enterprise” (Grönroos, C., 1996). Based on the study, it can be concluded that broadly two significant factors namely “*Service Responsiveness*” and “*Economic and Convenient Service Delivery*” have been identified in the automobile sector consisting of five variables namely “Speed/Promptness in the Service, Quality of Repair, Behaviour of the Management, Location of the Service Centre and Cost involved in the Service” which are having great influence towards predicting the customer satisfaction in regard to after sales service in the automobile sector.

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